

G+3 HOSPITAL BUILDING USING FLAT SLAB

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ABSTRACT:

The main purpose of our project is to satisfy the medical needs of people. In this project, we are concerned about the plan and design of the G+3 hospital building using a flat slab. The plan of the hospital building is done by using AutoCAD software. The design of the structure was done by using E-tabs as well as IS 456: 2000 Code, for plain and reinforced cement concrete. The main aim of this project is to design the plan for hospital building by using software techniques. The design of the hospital building should be developed with the following disciplines. Here the hospital building was planned and designed for a G+3 story structure. Analysis of the hospital building by using software technique, under this title we have discussed the various structures design procedure by limit state method. In this project, we have designed the flat slab, design of beam, design of the shear wall, and design of column. This is a G+3 structure. This project has M30 grade of concrete and Fe500 grade of steel used to design of the above structure. The analysis was done using the response spectrum method in ETABS software according to the rules and regulations of the Indian standard code

Keywords: response spectrum, limit state method,

CHAPTER NO 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 GENERAL:

Depending upon the size of town or city the type of hospital buildings. The people are treated for various diseases and also given advice in respect of health. They are also advised how to keep environment clean so as to avoid the slaughter of various diseases. For the purpose of clarification the building for health may be termed as dispensaries, clinics, maternity homes, nursing homes, laboratories, child welfare centers and general hospital. A dispensary used to mean a room where compounded. Now its meaning has been widened. Now dispensary means a place whose medicines are prescribed and given to the patients. It is not necessarily a single room but consists of doctor's room, pharmacy room, dressing room and waiting room. In Maternity homes and nursing homes both of them cares for special treatments. Here the patients are allowed to stay for short duration. This plot location is situated at sec-2A Ulwe, Navi Mumbai. It is located centrally in a quite place which is well connected by means of transport. It is situated near Uran highway so that it would be convenient for other people also. This design houses all the facilities keeping in mind the comfort level of the public in accessing those facilities. All departments of a hospital are included in the design and it is not only on structural grounds but also on ease in accessing the facilities within.

1.1.1 DESCRIPTION OF FLAT SLAB:

A flat slab is a two way reinforced concrete slab that usually does not have beams and girders and the loads are transferred directly to the supporting concrete column. They are subjected to both vertical and lateral loads. In general normal frame construction utilizes columns, slabs and beams. However it may be possible to undertake construction with out providing beams, in such a case the frame system would consist of slab and columns without beams. These types of flat slabs are called flat slabs, since their behavior resembles the bending of flat plates. Flat Slab is better understood as the slab without beams resting directly on supports (like columns & or walls). By virtue of that large Bending Moment & Shear Forces are developed close to the columns. Flat slabs system of construction is one in which the beams used in the conventional methods of constructions are done away with. The slab directly rests on the column and load from the slab is directly transferred to the columns and then to the foundation. To support heavy loads the thickness of slab near the support with the column is increased and these are called drops, or columns are generally provided with enlarged heads called column heads or capitals. Absence of beam gives a plain ceiling, thus giving better architectural appearance and also less vulnerability in case of fire than in usual cases where beams are used.

1.2 TYPES OF FLAT SLAB AND ITS FUNCTION:

Fig no: 1.2 flat slab types

We chose to go for flat slab with drop panel, its best suited for our load requirements and cross-sectional area of related components. The thickened part of a flat slab over its supporting column is technically known as drop panel. Drop panels increase the shear strength of the flat slab floor that means to resist shear. Drop panels increase the flat slab's negative moment capacity. Drop panels reduce deflection by stiffening the flat slabs.

1.2.1 APPLICATIONS OF FLAT SLAB:

- Large industrial structures, parking garages, ramps, warehouse, high rise building Health care centres , commercial building and hotel
- They are also used where use of beams are not required.
- Where structure require less formwork

1.2.2 BENEFITS OF FLAT SLAB:

- Flexibility of room
- Saving in building height.
- Shorter construction time.
- Ease of installation of M&E services.
- Use of prefabricated welded mesh.
- It reduces the overall height of the structure.
- Flat slabs are capable to carry concentrated loads.
- Requires less formwork.
- As reinforcement detailing of flat slabs is simple it is easy to place
- Better quality control.

1.3 METHOD TO DESIGN FLAT SLAB:

1.3.1 DIRECT DESIGN METHOD:

This method is used for determining the bending moment in the slab panel. In DDM, the recommendations apply to the gravity loading condition alone (not to lateral loading condition). In the direct design method, the total design moment for a span shall be determined for a strip bounded laterally by the centre-line of the pane) on each side of the centre-line of other supports. The direct design method gives rules for the determination of the total static design moment and its distribution between negative and positive moment sections.

LIMITATION:

- There must be at least three continuous spans in each direction.
- The panel should be rectangular, & the ratio of longer span to the shorter span within a panel shall not be greater than
- The successive span length in each direction shall not differ by more than one-third of the longer span.
- The end span may be shorter but not longer than the interior span.
- The design live load shall not exceed three times the design dead load.
- It shall be permissible to offset columns to a maximum of 10 percent of the span in the direction of the offset not with standing the provision.

1.3.2 EQUIVALENT FRAME METHOD:

The equivalent frame method (EFM) is widely used for the design of two-way reinforced concrete slab structures, and current design codes of practice permit the application of the EFM in analysing the flat plate slab structures under gravity and lateral loads. The EFM was, however, originally developed for the flat plate structures subjected to gravity load, which is not suitable for lateral loading case. Therefore, in this study, the first part of series research paper, proposed the structural analysis method for the flat plate slab structures under the combined gravity and lateral loads, which is named as the unified equivalent frame method (UEFM).

LIMITATIONS:

- The bending moments and shear forces may be determined by an analysis of the structure as a continuous frame and the following assumptions may be made:
- The structure shall be considered to be made up of equivalent frames on column lines taken longitudinally and transversely through the building.
- Each such frame may be analysed in its entirety, or, for vertical loading, each floor there of and the roof may be analysed separately with its columns being assumed fixed at their remote ends.
- For the purpose of determining relative stiffness of members. the moment of inertia of any slab or column may be assumed to be that of the gross cross-section of the concrete.

CHAPTER NO 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2. LITERATURE REVIEW:

A Brief review of previous studies on the planning, designing and analysis of hospital building using flat slab. This literature review focuses on the various methods, grades and software to design the flat slab. Literature is very helpful in understanding the different combinations of loads.

2.1 REVIEW OF LITERATURE: The review of some of the papers are as follow.

1. ANITHA M. et.al (April 2007):

As per Indian standard code they are using cube strength but in international standards cylindered are used which gives higher strength than cube. Drops are important criteria in increasing the shear strength of the slab. Enhance resistance to punching failure at the junction of concrete slab & column. By incorporating heads in slab, we are increasing rigidity of slab. In the interior span, the total design moments (M_o) are same for IS, NZS, ACI By comparing with different codes we concluded that ACI 318, NZS 3101 & euro codes are most effective in designing of flat slabs. The negative moment's section shall be designed to resist the larger of the two interior negative design moments for the span framing into common supports.

2. Jaya Prakash K. et.al (FEBRUARY-2016)

They studied the performance of flat slab and conventional slab structure subjected to various loads and conditions. To the study the behavior of both structure for the parameters like storey shear, storey displacement drift ratio, axial forces. Comparisons of flat and conventional building for the above parameters. Cost comparisons of various types of slabs available. After comparison of flat slab it is concluded that flat slab has many advantages over conventional slab and it can be very good option for modern construction demanding structural stability and state of art aesthetic aspect prospect.

3. Mohit Jain et.al (2016):

In this paper, The building models are analyzed for gravity load and seismic load and their results are then presented. The gravity load analysis gives performance of those models in absence of earthquake. Various seismic codes like FEMA 356, ASCE 41-06, Mexico Code, and Indian Standard recommend following two methods of analysis of reinforced concrete buildings. Seismic analysis- equivalent static analysis and response spectrum, it is observed that comparatively larger magnitude of lateral deformation has been observed in case of flat slab. This is due to decrease in lateral stiffness of flat slab system.

4. Atun Roy Chaudhary. et.al (April-2017)

For G+3 hospital building various load were live load, dead load, combination load were considered. The design by followed up by using IS code for better output of design consideration. The structural members were designed by obtaining results of analysis in a method of substitute frame basis

Geometric parameters – Beam=400X300mm Column=230X450m Slab=150mm.

Analyzing the planned structure to get a result of bending moment, shear force and axial force. Therefore, there is some minute difference between manual and software obtained results. Maximum moment and maximum shear force are the major consideration for planned structure to execute in the field.

5. Shete G. N. et.al (May 2017)

For analyzing and designing they have taken G+7 (an office building) with various shapes (rectangular and square). Sizes of flat slab are 6.8 mx6.4 m and 6.4 mx6.4 m providing with drop panel and without drop panel. Live load=3 KN/m² and floor finishing load=1 KN/m². Use M20 concrete and Fe415 steel. Flat slab

is designed by using direct design method. The properties of column size, drop panel size, slab thickness taken as per the design given as per IS 456-2000. Flat slab with drop: - C800x800 mm, S300 mm, D400 mm, Dead load = 7.5 KN/m^2 Flat slab without drop: - C1000x1000 mm, S400 mm, Dead load = 10 KN/m^2 . In flat slab building in both cases (manual design & software analysis) the results are satisfied for Punching Shear. The Design Base Shear is much higher in square slab as compared to rectangular slab building. Storey drift values for rectangular and square slab not have much variation.

6. Kiran Kumar. et.al (2018)

This paper analysis various studies carried out over planning, designing and analyzing a structure with the help of different software. All the studies considered gives a suggestion of adopting software for analyzing a building structure. The plinth area of this building is 2956 m^2 . This is a G+5 structure. This project has M25 grade of concrete and Fe415 grade of steel used to design of above structure. This project designed under limit state method which is more than other methods of designing. All the design procedure are followed code book are IS456-2000, Sp16-1980, National building code book-2005, the minister of health section 44 act 1977. Due to its flexibility and its provision for economic sections both in terms of steel and concrete, is adopted for further analysis procedure

7. NARESH K. (Aug 2019)

Displacement of industrial and commercial structure constructed using flat slab system is more than the conventional slab system. Here we can say that flat slab with shear wall gives better displacement resisting. With the increase in height of structure displacement is also goes on increasing. Story shear of Flat slab building is less than conventional slab building in Y-direction. Story shear is maximum at base level and it decreases as height of structure increases. Base shear of flat slab building is less than the base shear in conventional slab building in both X and Y directions. It is seen that story drift is maximum for the conventional slab compared to flat slab and very less for the flat slab with shear wall. Story stiffness of conventional slab building is stiffer than Flat slab building. As the story no decreases stiffness goes on increasing.

8. Prabhakaran N. (March 2019)

Planning analysis and designing of Hospital Building is our study which is to proposed. The framed type of construction is used for the construction and the designing of structure is carried out by limit state method with the IS 456: 2000 code. The analysis is carried out by using limit state method STAAD Pro. The availability of men and materials is in local itself. The plan and structural elements are designed using limit state method and the reinforced details has been obtained slabs and foundation has been designed using STAAD Pro also. This study helps us in exploring knowledge about planning analyzing and designing a Hospital Building.

9. Srikanth A. et.al (April 2020)

The main aim of this journal is to analyze the plan of hospital building by using software techniques The planning of a building is developed keeping in view, the building bye laws, environmental conditions prevailing in that area. Height of building is restricted as per the municipal authorities of the area. The drawings of plan are developed using auto cad software. The slabs are designed as per the code of practice IS 456 2000 in accordance to LSM. The imposed loads are noted from code of practice IS 875 1987. The analysis of frame is carried out in ETABS and the design of beam and columns are also carried out in ETABS. We can conclude that, hence by using software, we can analyze and design a building effectively by considering loads like Dead load, Live load, Wind load, Seismic load and their combinations. In this paper, software was used for analysis and design purpose mainly for the result of shear force and maximum bending moment. RCC detailing is of most important concern for clear understanding and also in executing the reinforcement work without any difficulty.

CHAPTER NO: 03

OBJECTIVE & METHODOLOGY

3.1 AIM:

- The main aim of this project is to present a functional plan and design of G+3 hospital building using flat slab at sector 02 Ulwe 410206

3.2 OBJECTIVE:

- To study and identify the need for the hospital over that location, to locate the hospital.
- To prepare functional plan of the hospital building.
- To prepare structural plan of the hospital building.
- To Prepare a model for analysis using E- TABS.
- Analysis and design of building
- Comparison of flat slab model with conventional slab model in terms of bending moment, shear values, etc
- Comparative study of flat slab and conventional slab based on seismic analysis using response spectrum method

3.3 METHODOLOGY

The Analysis of building structure with the help of “Extended 3D Analysis Building Structure” ETABS 2018 software.

plot selection

(noticing that there is need of high bedded occupancy hospital in the area, plot was selected around a residential area)

planning

(layout plan for this hospital building was prepared on autodesks autocad, with respect to IS Code 12433 part 2)

structural planning (flat slab) conventional.

(structural plan that involved positioning of the column, beam, drop panel, column strips, middle strips and other structural components are depicted)

analysis of building model (flat slab) conv.

(analysis of the same model flat slab as well as conventional slab-beam system is done as required, with modular checks performed)

designing of model (software & manual) flat slab & conventional.

(designing of same two models are designed on csi etabs software with manual design done for panels involed in each model as set in IS Code 456:2000)

comparing behaviour under conditional loads for both models

(its behaviour such as bending moment, shear forces, axial loading under applied loads and its combination)

seismic analysis

(seismic reports are prepared for both models after applying earthquake loads and observed the behaviour and compared the two, using response spectrum method)

CHAPTER NO 4

FUNCTIONAL PLAN

4.1 FUNCTIONAL PLAN

Functional planning is an analytical process in hospital planning and development which includes definition of fictional requirements, area requirements and work flow to meet the needs and priorities of the medical programme. In consideration of the medical programme, the hospital is to have a balanced combination of the following functional areas and services For basic hospital building ,we have IS 12433 part 1 to part 4 depending upon the bed requirements.

- IS 12433 part:1 for 30 beds.
- IS 12433 part:2 for 100 beds.
- IS 12433 part:3 for 200 beds.
- IS 12433 part:4 for 300 beds

We have adopted IS 12433 (Part 2)

Fig no: 4.1.1 Ground Floor plan

Fig no: 4.1.2 First Floor Plan

Fig no:4.1.3 Second Floor Plan

Fig no: 4.1.4 Third Floor Plan

CHAPTER NO 5 STRUCTURAL PLAN

5.1 GUIDELINE TO FLAT SLAB STRUCTURE:

Column strip - Column strip means a design strip having a width of $0.25l_2$, but not greater than $0.25l_1$ on each side of the column centreline, where l_1 is the span in the direction moments are being determined, measured centre to centre of supports and l_2 is the span transverse IS 456: 2000 toll' measured centre to centre of supports.

Middle strip - Middle strip means a design strip bounded on each of its opposite sides by the column strip.

Panel: Panel means that part of a slab bounded on each of its four sides by the centre-line of a column or centre-lines of adjacent spans.

Drop: The drops when provided shall be rectangular in plan. and have a length in each direction not less than one-third of the panel length in that direction. For exterior panels. the width of drops at right angles to the noncontinuous edge and measured from the centre-line of the columns shall be equal to one-half the width of drop for interior panels.

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Fig no: 5.1.1 ground floor plan

Fig no 5.1.2: First Floor Plan

Fig no:5.1.3 Second Floor Plan

Fig no :5.1.4 Third Floor Plan

5.1.1 STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS:

It may be said as the determination of effects (like shear force, bending moment, deflection, etc..) of different loads acting on the structures and on their corresponding elements. Structures like buildings, bridges, flyovers, ,tunnels, towers, etc., done with the analysis must withstand the forces acting on it by ensuring the safety to the

occupants. Structural analysis is the integration of various fields like applied mechanics, material science and applied mathematics to compute a structure's deformations, internal forces, support reactions, stress, accelerations, and stability. The results of this analysis are used to assess the structure's caliber for use. Structural analysis thus plays a vital role in the engineering design of structures

5.1.2 INPUT DATA

Dead Load: It mainly consists of self-weight of structure. Dead load calculations are done as per IS 875 (part 1) – 1987

Floor finish: Floor finish taken as 2KN/m²

Wall Load: external wall load for conventional slab: $(0.2*(3.8-0.6)*14) = 8.96\text{KN/m}$

Internal wall load for conventional slab: $(0.15*(3.8-0.6)*14) = 6.7\text{KN/m}$

External wall load for flat slab: $(0.2*(3.8-0.6)*14) = 8.96\text{KN/m}$

Internal wall load for flat slab: $(0.15*(3.8-0.4)*14) = 1.14\text{KN/m}$

Wall load for parapet wall for both model: $0.2*1.2*14 = 3.63\text{KN/m}$

Live Load: Live load conditions are considered according to IS 875 (part 2) – 1987

Live Load: on floors taken as 4KN/m²

Live Load on terrace taken as 1.5KN/m²

Live Load for lift on terrace level taken as 3KN/m²

Water proofing on terrace: 3 kN/m²

External wall AAC block: 200 mm thick

Internal wall AAC block: 150 mm thick

External wall AAC block, Parapet :200 mm thick

Concrete Grade: M30 for wall & column M30 for beams and slabs Reinforcement grade Fe500

Density of concrete: 25 KN/m³

No. of story G+3 Above floor+Terrace

Floorheight:3.8 m

Parapet wall height: 1.2m

Depth of slab:250 mm for conventional beam & slab system and 250mm for Flat slab and 400mm Drop panel

Type of slab shell element

Beam size:300X600mm for conventional beam and slab system 300X600mm peripheral beam for flat slab system

Column size: 600mmx600mm Wall thickness 300 mm Spacing between frame 6m Floor dimension in x direction 49.8 m Floor dimension in y direction 49.8 m

Slab type: shell thin

Wall type: shell thin

5.1.3 Seismic Load Parameter:

Earthquake load shall be calculated as per IS 1893 – 2016.

Sr.no	Parameter	Value	Remarks
1	Seismic Zone	III	Navi Mumbai
2	Zone Factor (Z)	0.16	
3	Importance factor (I)	1.5	PUBLIC BLDG. (hospital)
4	Response Reduction factor (R)	3 for Flat slab system	
5	Type of soil	I	HARD

5.1.4 Wind Load Parameter as per IS 875 (part 3)

Sr.no	Parameter	Value
1	Location	ULWE
2.	Wind speed	44m/s
3.	Terrain category	3
4.	Probability Factor, k1	1
5.	Topography Factor, k3	1

5.2 Etabs analysis and design procedure

- Extract file from autocad
- Define Material Properties
- Define Frame Sections
- Define Slab Sections
- Define Load Cases
- Draw Beam Objects (Frame Members)
- Draw Column Objects (Frame Members)
- Assign Slab Sections
- Assign Restraints
- Assign Slab Loads
- View Input Data in Tabular Form
- Run the Analysis
- View Analysis Results Graphically
- Design Concrete Frame Element

Fig no:5.2.1 Base (Model 1: flat slab and model 2: conventional slab)

Fig no: 5.2.2 Plinth (Model 1: flat slab and model 2: conventional slab)

Fig no: 5.2.3 First Floor Plan (Model 1: flat slab model)

Fig no: 5.2.4 First Floor Plan (Model 2: conventional slab)

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Fig no: 5.2.5 3-Dimensional view (Model 1: flat slab)

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Fig no: 5.2.6 3-Dimensional view (Model 2: conventional slab)

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5.2.1 Column forces for flat slab

Limit state of strength:

1. UDcon 1: 1.5DL
2. UDcon 2: 1.5DL+1.5LL
3. UDcon 19 and UDcon 21: 1.5DL+1.5EQ
4. UDcon 23 and UDcon 25: 0.9DL +1.5EQ
5. UDcon 27 and UDcon 28: 1.2DL+1.2LL+1.2EQ

STOREY	COLUMN NO.	LOAD COMBO	P	V2	V3	T	M2	M3
1	C22	UDCon1	-1384.70	-11.93	-37.83	-1.01	-57.68	-15.46
1	C22	UDcon2	-1686.07	-14.74	-49.26	-1.44	-66.67	-18.14
1	C22	UDCon19	-1626.35	24.68	-39.44	-0.63	2.92	21.40
1	C22	UDCon21	-1298.65	-8.86	-22.17	-0.46	-3.24	-6.63
1	C22	UDCon23	-1094.07	29.45	-24.31	-0.22	-37.31	68.78
1	C22	UDCon25	-744.76	-4.08	-7.03	-0.06	19.82	-0.44
1	C22	UDCon27	-1059.18	28.03	-34.44	1.526	-39.03	68.54
1	C22	UDCon28	-1263.86	-11.25	-25.01	-0.98	-7.36	-13.49

Table no:5.2.1 Column Forces For Flat Slab

5.2.2 Column forces for conventional slab

Limit state of strength:

1. UDcon 1: 1.5DL
2. UDcon 2: 1.5DL+1.5LL
3. UDcon 19 and UDcon 21: 1.5DL+1.5EQ
4. UDcon 23 and UDcon 25: 0.9DL +1.5EQ
5. UDcon 27 and UDcon 28: 1.2DL+1.2LL+1.2EQ

STOREY	COLUMN NO.	LOAD COMBO	P	V2	V3	T	M2	M2
1	C22	UDCon1	-1484.58	-12.58	-37.64	-0.72	-57.88	-16.31
1	C22	UDCon2	-1795.71	-15.15	-46.99	-1.02	-65.36	-18.88
1	C22	UDCon19	-1708.32	22.70	-39.10	-0.34	-60.63	63.56
1	C22	UDCon21	-1366.03	-9.22	-18.83	-0.30	-1.52	-6.66
1	C22	UDCon23	-1114.49	27.72	-24.04	-0.05	-37.48	70.09
1	C22	UDCon25	-772.20	-4.21	-3.77	-0.01	21.62	-0.13
1	C22	UDCon27	-1160.18	28.70	-31.41	2.47	-35.26	75.28
1	C22	UDCon28	-1308.22	-8.90	-20.62	-0.22	-3.83	-7.70

Table no: 5.2.2 Column Forces of Conventional Slab

5.2.3 Beam forces of flat slab:

Limit state of strength:

1. UDcon 1: 1.5DL
2. UDcon 2: 1.5DL+1.5LL
3. UDcon 19 and UDcon 21: 1.5DL+1.5EQ
4. UDcon 23 and UDcon 25: 0.9DL +1.5EQ
5. UDcon 27 and UDcon 28: 1.2DL+1.2LL+1.2EQ

STOREY	BEAM NO.	LOAD COMBO	P	V2	V3	T	M2	M3
1	B36	UDCon1	0	-0.48	0	0.00002	0	0.18
1	B36	UDCon2	0	-0.74	0	0.000028	0	0.33
1	B36	UDCon19	0	-0.48	0	-0.0001	0	-0.18
1	B36	UDCon21	0	-0.36	0	7.668E-06	0	-0.105
1	B36	UDCon23	0	-0.29	0	-0.0001	0	-0.1118
1	B36	UDCon25	0	-0.17	0	0	0	-0.0322
1	B36	UDCon27	0	-0.58	0	0.0001	0	0.261
1	B36	UDCon28	0	-0.51	0	0.000023	0	-0.201

Table no: 5.2.3 Beam forces for Flat Slab

5.2.4 Beam forces for conventional slab:

Limit state of strength:

1. UDcon 1: 1.5DL
2. UDcon 2: 1.5DL+1.5LL
3. UDcon 19 and UDcon 21: 1.5DL+1.5EQ
4. UDcon 23 and UDcon 25: 0.9DL +1.5EQ
5. UDcon 27 and UDcon 28: 1.2DL+1.2LL+1.2EQ

STOREY	BEAM NO.	LOAD COMBO	P	V2	V3	T	M2	M3
1	B36	UDCon1	0	-97.04	0	-0.004	0	-72.49
1	B36	UDCon2	0	-138.0	0	-0.007	0	-104.11
1	B36	UDcon19	0	-100.8	0	-0.035	0	-75.69
1	B36	UDcon23	0	-87.26	0	0.0051	0	-51.87
1	B36	UDcon25	0	-102.3	0	0.0585	0	-86.83
1	B36	UDCon27	0	-95.31	0	-0.0004	0	-59.15
1	B36	UDCon28	0	-72.51	0	-0.013	0	-29.02

Table no: 5.2.4 Beam forces of Conventional Slab

5.2.5 Shear values for flat slab:

Limit state of strength:

1. UDcon 1: 1.5DL
2. UDcon 2: 1.5DL+1.5LL
3. UDcon 19 and UDcon 21: 1.5DL+1.5EQ
4. UDcon 23 and UDcon 25: 0.9DL +1.5EQ
5. UDcon 27 and UDcon 28: 1.2DL+1.2LL+1.2EQ

STOREY	PIER	LOAD COMBO	P	V2	V3	T	M2	M3
1	SW1	UDCon1	-1044.0	3.63	33.02	5.32	-56.75	-72.26
1	SW1	UDCon2	-1244.1	-3.26	49.44	9.19	-83.65	-108.05
1	SW1	UDCon19	-55.50	171.62	19.20	7.39	-5250	-144.40
1	SW1	UDCon23	362.11	170.11	5.99	-9.52	-29.79	-115.50
1	SW1	UDCon25	813.18	831.42	-2.89	-17.71	0.92	2422.02
1	SW1	UDCon27	-339.94	345.85	49.32	22.91	-63.18	125.38
1	SW1	UDCon28	-361.87	726.89	45.93	23.84	-65.69	390.45

Table no: 5.2.5 Shear values for Flat Slab

5.2.6 Shear values for conventional slab:

Limit state of strength:

1. UDcon 1: 1.5DL
2. UDcon 2: 1.5DL+1.5LL
3. UDcon 19 and UDcon 21: 1.5DL+1.5EQ
4. UDcon 23 and UDcon 25: 0.9DL +1.5EQ
5. UDcon 27 and UDcon 28: 1.2DL+1.2LL+1.2EQ

STOREY	PIER	LOAD COMBO	P	V2	V3	T	M2	M3
1	SW1	UDCon1	-948.82	12.098	15.52	-2.13	-28.34	-59.65
1	SW1	UDCon2	-1139.4	9.47	23.73	-1.68	-42.03	-94.11
1	SW1	UDCon19	62.12	190.58	3.80	-13.26	-28.10	-127.03
1	SW1	UDCon23	441.63	185.74	-2.40	-12.41	-16.76	-103.1
1	SW1	UDCon25	277.91	861.31	1.45	-18.38	-15.10	475.89
1	SW1	UDCon27	-99.92	452.35	29.56	16.36	-30.60	184.4
1	SW1	UDCon28	-99.65	850.96	28.04	16.74	-31.05	460.65

Table no: 5.2.6 Shear Values for Conventional Slab

5.5 E-TABS BASED DESIGN MOMENTS FOR FLAT SLAB AND CONVENTIONAL SLAB

Fig no:5.5.1 conventional slab moments (along – X direction)

Research Through Innovation

Fig no:5.5.2 conventional slab moments (along Y direction)

Fig no:5.5.3 Flat slab moments (column and middle strip along X - direction)

Fig no:5.5.4 flat slab moments (column and middle strip along Y - direction)

CHAPTER NO 6

MANUAL CALCULATION

6.1 Manual calculation for flat slab:

Considering load combination DL+LL for panel size 6m X 5m

Fig no: 6.1.1 Slab Panel (6m X 5m)

Fig no: 6.1.2 vertical strip moment

flat slab design: as per IS 456:2000

Data: panel size: 6m X 5m
 Live load; 4KN/m²
 Floor finish: 2KN/m²
 Ly: 6m
 Lx:5m
 Drop size 2.3m X 3m

Solution: (boundary conditions: interior panel thickness)

Step1: since HYSD steel is used as drop is provide maximum span to thickness ratio is permitted as 32

Thickness of flat slab = $5000/32 = 156.25\text{mm}$ equal to 200mm

Overall depth (thickness) D: $200+20+5 = 250\text{mm}$

Let the drop be of 400mm (drop panel)

Hence D = 250mm

Drop = $250+400$
 = 680mm

Step 2: size of drop : (it shall not be less than $1/3 \times 6 = 2\text{m}$ and $1/3 \times 5 = 1.667\text{m}$)

Longer span = 2.7m

Shorter span = 2m

For vertical strip

Minimum depth of drop panel = $1/4 * 250 = 62.5\text{mm}$

Horizontal column strip = middle strip = 3m

Vertical column strip = middle strip = 2.5m

Step 3: load calculations:

(For the purpose of design let us take self-weight as that due to thickness at column – strip)

Self-weight: $0.65 * 1 * 25 = 16.25\text{KN/m}^2$

Live load: 4KN/m

Floor finish: 2KN/m

Total load: 22.25KN/m^2

Factored total load: $1.5 * 22.25\text{KN/m}^2$

Clear span: $5-0.6 = 4.4\text{m}$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Design load } W_o &: W_u * L_x * L_n \\ &= 33.375 * 5 * 4.4 \\ &= \mathbf{750.94\text{KN/m}}\end{aligned}$$

Step 4: design total moment, Cl.31.4.2.2)

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total moment } M_o &: W_o * l_n / 8 \\ &= 750.94 * 4.4 / 8 \\ &: \mathbf{.422.404\text{KN}}\end{aligned}$$

As per clause 31.4.3.2

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total negative moment} &: 0.65 * 422.404 \\ &= \mathbf{274.56\text{KN/m}}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Total positive moment} &: 0.35 * 422.404 \\ &= \mathbf{147.841\text{KN/m}}\end{aligned}$$

The above moments are to be distributed into column strip and middle strip

Type	Column strip	Middle strip
-ve moment	$0.75 * 274.56 = 206\text{KNm}$	$0.25 * 274.56 = 68.64\text{KNm}$
+ve moment	$0.6 * 147.841 = 88.704\text{KNm}$	$0.4 * 147.841 = 59.13\text{KNm}$

Step 5: width of strip, L_x

$$\text{Column strip} = \text{middle strip} = 2500\text{mm}$$

Width of strip, L_y

$$\text{Column strip} = \text{middle strip} = 3000\text{mm}$$

$$\begin{aligned}M_{ulim} &= 0.133 * f_{ck} * b * d^2 \\ &= 0.133 * 30 * 2500 * 630^2 \\ &= 3959.1 * 10^6 \text{ Nmm} \\ &= \mathbf{3959.1\text{KNm}}\end{aligned}$$

Therefore M_{ulim} greater than M_u (hence thickness selected is sufficient)

For horizontal strips:

$$\text{Vertical width of column strip: } 0.25l_1 = 1.5\text{m}$$

$$\text{Horizontal width of column strip: } 0.25l_2 = 1.25\text{m}$$

$$\text{Vertical width of middle strip: } 3\text{m}$$

$$\text{Horizontal width of middle strip: } 2.5\text{m}$$

Load calculation:

$$\text{Self weight} = 0.65 * 1 * 25 = 16.25 \text{ KN/m}$$

Floor finish = 2KN/m

Live load: 4KN/m

Total load: 22.25 KN/m

Factored load = $1.5 \times 22.25 = \text{KN/m}$

Clear span = $6 - 0.6 = 5.4\text{m} = l_n$

Design load (W_o) = $W_u \times l_2 \times l_3$

$$= 33.375 \times 6 \times 5.4 = 1081.35\text{KN}$$

Design Total moment:

Total moment: $M_o = W_o l_n / 8$

$$= 1081.35 \times 5.4 / 8$$

$$= 729.91\text{KNm}$$

As per clause 31.4.3.2

Total negative moment = 0.65×729.91

$$= 474.44\text{KNm}$$

Total positive moment = 0.35×729.91

$$= 255.47\text{KNm}$$

The above moments are to be distributed into column strip and middle strip

Type	Column strip	Middle strip
-ve moment	$0.75 \times 474.44 = 353.58$	$0.25 \times 474.44 = 118.61$
+ve moment	$0.6 \times 255.47 = 153.28$	$0.4 \times 255.47 = 102.19$

Width of strip:

Width of strip, l_x

Column strip = middle strip = 2500mm

Width of strip l_y

Column strip = middle strip = 3000mm

6.2 Manual calculation for conventional slab (two-way slab)

Data : Panel Size: 6m X 5m

Live load; 4 KN/m²

Floor finish: 2 KN/m²

L_y : 6m

L_x : 5m

M30, Fe500

Solution: (Boundary conditions: Interior Panel)

Step 1 : Check for type of of Slab,

$$L_y = 6\text{m} = 6000\text{mm}$$

Centre to Centre distance of Shorter Slab,

$$L_x = 5\text{m} = 5000\text{mm}$$

$$L_y/L_x = 6000/5000 = 1.2 < 2 \text{ (Two – Way Slab System)}$$

Step 2 : Preliminary Dimensions,

Thickness of Slab,

$$d = L_x / B.V * M.F = 5000 / 26 * 1.1 = 174.824$$

$$= \mathbf{200\text{mm}}$$

assuming Pt% as 0.4%

$$F_s = 0.58 * 500 = 290$$

$$M.F = 1.1$$

assuming Cover as 25mm & 10mm Diameter bars,

$$\text{Overall Depth (D)} = 200 + 20 + 5 = 225\text{mm}$$

$$= \mathbf{250\text{mm}}$$

$$d_x = 250 - 20 - 5 = \mathbf{225\text{mm}}$$

$$d_y = 200 - 10 = \mathbf{190\text{mm}}$$

Step 3 : Effective Span,

$$\text{for } L_x = 5000 + 225 = \mathbf{5225\text{mm}}$$

$$\text{for } L_y = 6000 + 190 = \mathbf{6190\text{mm}}$$

Step 4 : Load Calculation,

$$1. \text{ Self-weight} = 25 * 0.25 = 6.25 \text{ KN/m}^2$$

$$2. \text{ Live Load} = 4 \text{ KN/m}^2$$

$$3. \text{ Floor Finish} = 2 \text{ KN/m}^2$$

$$\text{Total Load} = \mathbf{13.25 \text{ KN/m}^2}$$

$$\text{Factored Load} = 1.5 * 13.25 = \mathbf{19.875 \text{ KN/m}^2}$$

Step 5: Moment Calculations,

$$M_{ux} = \alpha_x * w_u * L_{ex}^2$$

$$M_{uy} = \alpha_y * w_u * L_{ey}^2$$

Shorter Span Moment Coefficient,

$$\text{-ve moment coefficient, } \alpha_x = \mathbf{0.043}$$

$$\text{+ve moment coefficient, } \alpha_x = \mathbf{0.082}$$

Longer Span Moment Coefficient,

-ve moment coefficient, $\alpha_y^- = 0.032$

+ve moment coefficient, $\alpha_y^+ = 0.024$

Shorter Span Moment,

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Mu}(-ve) &= \alpha_x^- * w * Lx^2 \\ &= 0.043 * 19.875 * (5.225)^2 \\ &= \mathbf{23.332 \text{ KN-m}}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Mu}(+ve) &= \alpha_x^+ * w * Lx^2 \\ &= 0.032 * 19.875 * (5.225)^2 \\ &= \mathbf{17.363 \text{ KN-m}}\end{aligned}$$

Longer Span Moment,

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Mu}(-ve) &= \alpha_y^- * w * Lx^2 \\ &= 0.032 * 19.875 * (5.225)^2 \\ &= \mathbf{17.363 \text{ KN-m}}\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\text{Mu}(+ve) &= \alpha_y^+ * w * Lx^2 \\ &= 0.024 * 19.875 * (5.225)^2 \\ &= \mathbf{13.022 \text{ KN-m}}\end{aligned}$$

CHAPTER NO 7

RESPONSE SPECTRUM

7 Response spectrum: (as per IS 1893:2016 Part 1 Cl.3.22)

It is the representation of maximum responses of a spectrum of idealized single degree freedom systems of different natural periods but having the same damping, under the action of the same earthquake ground motion at their bases.

Fig no: 7.1 Shows variation in lateral force, base shear and storey shear due to ground motion

7.1 Storey displacement: It is the lateral displacement of the storey relative to the base. Providing drops to flat slab storey displacement reduces slightly as stiffness increases slightly

MAXIMUM STORY DISPLACEMENT SPEC X

Fig no: 7.1.1 Model 1: flat slab

In storey displacement considering load SPEC X here we have got maximum displcement values at terrace and minimum at plinth

MAXIMUM DISPLACEMENT LOAD - SPEC X

Fig no:7.1.2 Model 2: conventional slab

For conventional slab the maximum displcement is at terrace level 16.21 in x – direction and minimum at plinth level in y direction

7.2 Storey drift: It is the relative displacement between the floors above and below the storey under consideration. As per IS1893:2016 storey drift in any storey shall not exceed 0.004 times the storey height.

Fig no: 7.2.1 Model 1: flat slab

In storey drift considering load spec x, storey drift is at all floor is under IS CODE limittaions.

Fig no:7.2.2 Model 2: conventional slab

In storey drift considering load spec x, storey drift is at all floor is under IS CODE limittaions.

7.3 Storey shear: It is the sum of design lateral forces at all levels above the storey under consideration.
 storey shear values increase from model 1 to model 2 as weight of the structure increases from model 1 to model 2

STORY SHEAR (KN) LOAD - SPEC X

Fig no: 7.3.1 Model 1: flat slab

In storey shear considering load spec x the maximum storey shear is at plinth level I x – direction and minimum at terrace level in y – direction.

STORY SHEAR (KN) LOAD - SPEC X

Fig no: 7.3.2 Model 2: conventional slab

In storey shear considering load spec x the maximum storey shear is at 1st floor level In x – dircetion and in y – direction.

CHAPTER NO 8

CONCLUSION

Conclusion:

Functional plan, structural plan and Model of hospital building is created using softwares over the selected location.

(it is observed that flat slab planning can be more easier as the head clearance is acquired and partition walls can be putten as required, where as in slab beam system beams take head room and walls has to be in specific positions.

in structural plan as both moodels bears the same combination of loads and involve almost same rc structures other than drop panel in one and beams in another, in flat slab addition of column strip and middle strip is considered as well.)

Analysis and design of flat slab system and conventional slab system and its behaviour under combination of loads is noted.

Comparison between the two models according to Maximum Bending Moments and Axial force developed on Column,behaviour of Beams and Strips are recorded respectively.

manual calculation for flat slab syatem-

(shorter span (-ve) = **274.56KNm**, shorter span (+ve) = **147.841KNm**

longer span (-ve) = **474.44KNm**, longer span (+ve) = **255.47KNm**)

manual calculation for convensional slab-beam system-

(Shorter span (-ve) = **23.332 KN-m**, Shorter span (+ve) = **17.363 KN-m**

Longer span (-ve) = **17.363 KN-m**, Longer span (+ve) = **13.022 KN-m**)

Behaviour of both models undergoing seismic changes, considering parameters such as Storey drift, Storey displacement and Storey shear is noted as well.

(seismic behaviour of flat slab gives more positive result than slab beam system considering parameters such as storey displacement, storey drift and storey shear with required limitations.)

(maximum storey displacement for flat slab came out as **14.45** in x-direction and **5.61** in y-direction for tarrace.)

(maximum storey displacement for convensional slab system is at terrace level **16.21** in x – direction and **7.02** in y-direction.)

(maximum storey drift for flat slab is **0.00096** in x-direction and **0.0003708** in y-direction.)

(maximum storey drift for convensional slab system **0.001** in x-direction and **0.00046** in y-direction.)

(maximum storey shear for flat slab is **13770.19** in x-direction and **32.76** in y-direction.)

(maximum storey shear for convensional slab beam system is **14333.72** in x-direction and **66.55** in y-direction.)

All Regular and Seismic parameter values have fallen under limitations provided that means both the models have successfully passed whereas flat slab gives more positive results whether that is Bending moment, shear forces, axial loading, Storey Displacement, Storey Drift or Storey Shear in the structure is less than in convensional slab-beam system.

CHAPTER NO 9

REFERENCES

Codes in practice -

INDIAN STANDARD CODES-

IS 456 : 2000, Plain and RCC Structures

IS 875 : 1987, For design loads (building and structures)

IS 1893 : 2016, Criteria for earthquake resistant design structures

IS 12433 : 2001, Basic requirements for hospital planning

References -

- Dr. N. Ashok kumar, M. Navaneethan, B. Naviya , D. Gopalakrishnan, Arun Roy Choudhury, Planning, Analysis, and Design of Hospital Building using STAAD PRO
- Sankar J, Raghava Rao E. V, Chennakesavulu N, design of G+4 Hospital Building for earthquake resistant, Visakha technical campus, Visakhapatnam, INDIA
- Shekharsingh Suryawanshi, Utkarsh Mange, Tejas Gorle, Saurabh Charde, Shubham Kedar, Dr. B. V. Khode, seismic analysis of multistoreyed G+8 RCC Frame Building for different seismic zones in Nagpur, Civil Dept. G.H. Raisonni College of Engineering Nagpur, Maharashtra, India,
- M. V. K. Satish, K. Bhavana, production based design and analysis of a new hospital building subjected to impact load using staad pro. Kakinada Institute of Technology and sciences
- C. Priyanka¹ M. Priyanka² V. Kumaran³, planning , analysis and design of multispeciality hospital building, Loyola Institute of Technology, India
- Kiran kumar, K. E. Pravin, planning, analysis and design of G+5 Hospital building using STAAD PRO.
- Abhishek Mehta, “Study of substitute frame method of analysis for lateral loading conditions”, Department of Civil Engineering, National Institute of Technology.
- Aman, Manjunath Nalwadgi, Vishal T, Gajendra. “Analysis and design of multistorey building by using STAAD Pro”, International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology (IRJET), Volume: 03 Issue: 06, 2016.
- American Institute of Architects (AIA), “Guidelines for Design and Construction of Hospital and Health Care Facilities”: 2006 edition.
- Divyakmath, K. Vandana Reddy, “Analysis and Design of reinforced concrete structures- G+5 building model”. mini project report, GokarajuRangaraju Institute of Engineering and Technology, Hyderabad, India- 2012.

- Park et al. (2008) found that equivalent frame method is not appropriate in accurately predicting the response of two-way slab systems under lateral loads. Currently design .code, aci 318-05[2.1] permit the efm for the analysis of two-way slab system under gravity loads and lateral loads such as seismic loads.
- Subramanian et al (2005) found that to increase the punching shear strength of flat slab, the shear reinforcement is found to provide economical solution. They not only enhance the shear capacity but also result in flexural failure of the slab and thus increasing the ductility of flat slab, which is very important in earthquake prone zone.
- Patel S. S. and Sigi R. (2014). Analysis and Design of Flat Plat Slabs Using Various Codes, International Journal of Research in Science & Technology (IJReT)

